

THE MODEL OF INCREASING EFFICIENCY, MODERN ENTERPRISE ADMINISTRATION, RESIDENTIAL, APARTMENT RENTAL IN HUA HIN DISTRICT, PRACHUAP KHIRI KHAN PROVINCE

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Abstract

Covid-19 pandemic situation the impact on the tourism services business, as well as the residential real estate business, has led to a decline in tenants doing business with tourists. It is currently undergoing economic revitalization, including the business adaptation of apartment-for-rent housing. If the successful results of the rental apartment housing enterprise are studied, it will greatly affect competition and improve the quality of services. This research aims to 1) To study the level of corporate management, customer base building, value selection, resident behavior, and the effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-for-rent housing 2) To study the influence of corporate management, customer base building, value selection, and resident behavior on the effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-for-rent housing and 3) To study the model of increasing the effectiveness of modern enterprise management, residential units, apartments for rent. It uses a combination of quantitative research and qualitative research. For quantitative research, the sample is entrepreneurs and employees, 300 people. The sample size is determined by 20 times the observed variables. Geospatial sampling, querying, and data analysis with structural equation models. For qualitative research, the data was collected by in-depth interviews with 15 rental apartment operators. Used specific selection methods and analyze data with content-based analysis. The results showed that 1) corporate management, customer base building, value selection, resident behavior, and the effectiveness of modern corporate management in rental apartments are high 2) Corporate management, customer base building, value, selection, and resident behavior directly influence the effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-rental and 3) increasing efficiency starting from the management of the organization. Resident behavior, value selection, and customer base building. By effectively managing modern enterprises, housing, apartments, rents are a destination that indicates success. The findings suggest that increasing success in the rental apartment business requires relevant factors linked together by causal factors to determine the work, while simultaneously benefiting the average rental apartment operator to adopt the model in the organization and learn in the academic circle of educators in the future.

Keywords: Corporate Management / Building Customer Base / Value Selection / Resident Behavior / Efficiency, Modern Enterprise Administration, Residential, Apartment Rental

Introduction

In the current situation, business competition continues to increase. Even if business operations are currently affected by the spread of the novel corona virus or COVID-19, organizations need to adapt to changing circumstances, competitors, and lifestyle habits of their customers. Finding ways or strategies that satisfy customers, meet their needs as much as possible, so that customers can return to use products and services continuously. This is for sustainable corporate performance and better business partners whose popular corporate strategy is implemented and business suitability consists of concepts. "Management Strategy for a New Age Organization" or "New Paradigm

Marketing Communication", which is a mass customization strategy that prioritizes high interaction with customers. The concept aims to meet the needs of individual customers and aims to build a lasting relationship with customers and believes that once they meet their needs, they will have a better experience that will create a greater sense of satisfaction. (Michelli, 2015; Sheth, Sisodia & Sharma, 2000; Siriwan Sribhithpaisan and Papaporn Chaihanchanchai, 2018, p. 63).

The real estate business on apartments for rent, Hua Hin District, Prachuap Khiri Khan Province is one of the areas of the country where rental apartment real estate businesses are operated for services to customers in large numbers, especially coastal areas, and there is high competition of business competitors. With Hua Hin being a unique tourist city and a thriving city as a main city, the real estate market has sprung up significantly to accommodate the arrival of Thais and foreigners. Hua Hin is likely to grow in the real estate market and the Thai market with an increasing number of tourists in the country, the rental apartment real estate business is one of the key factors in accommodating Thais and foreigners who come to rent for residential purposes for occupation or for short- and long-term tourism purposes (NovaBizz, 2018, para. 1-3).

Post-COVID-19 circumstances everything will be healed, relieved and solved. To restore the social, economic, business, tourism and service sectors, etc., so that all business sectors operate to normal and continue to develop through internal mechanisms such as management, people, knowledge, resources to surpass competitors and achieve business success as the ultimate goal of the organization. Therefore, the researchers were interested in studying the benefits of business competition for real estate operators in relation to apartment rentals, and the research title was "The Model of increasing efficiency, modern enterprise administration, residential, apartment rental in Hua Hin district, Prachuap Khiri Khan Province".

Research Objectives

- 1) To study the level of corporate management, customer base building, value, selection, resident behavior, and the effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-for-rent housing.
- 2) To study the influence of corporate management, customer base building, value, selection, and resident behavior on the effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-for-rent housing.
- 3) To study the model of increasing the effectiveness of modern enterprise management, residential units, apartments for rent.

Research hypothesis

- 1) Organizational management affects the creation of a customer base.
- 2) Managing the organization and building a customer base affects value selection.
- 3) Corporate management, customer base building, and value selection affect resident behavior.
- 4) Corporate management, customer base building, value, selection, and resident behavior impact the effectiveness of modern corporate management strategies for rental apartments.

Research Scope

This research used the mixed method is quantitative research to determine the influence of factors affecting the effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-rental housing, and qualitative research to support the effective management of modern enterprise management in rental apartments.

Research Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Modern organizational management enhancement patterns, apartment-rental housing

Research Methodology

1. Quantitative Research

The sample was 300 rental apartment operators and employees using a threshold of 20 times the observed variables (Grace, 2008, p. 15) Stratified sampling. The tool was a questionnaire. Analyze data with descriptive statistics and structural equation model analysis.

The tools used in the research are questionnaires on organizational management. Building a customer base, selecting a value Occupancy behavior and the effectiveness of modern corporate management of apartment-for-rent housing, 75 items. Five levels of estimation, individual IOC values equal to 0.67-1.00, confidence values for the entire questionnaire were .96. Analyze data using descriptive statistics and structural equation models to test the relationship between latent variables and observed variables and the relationship between independent variables and variables followed by the LISREL program.

2. Qualitative Research

The group of key contributors includes apartment operators consisting of 15 people. The tools are structured interviews, open-ended questions. Data is collected from in-depth interviews, individual key contributors. Used the data obtained to analyze the content, categorize opinions, organize primary and secondary issues to support quantitative research and create models for increasing the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from this research, researchers reported three objective findings and a model of structural equations in the following order:

1. Summary of objective 1 findings to study the level of corporate management, customer base building, value, selection, resident behavior, and the effectiveness of modern corporate management in rental apartments. The effectiveness of modern corporate management of apartment-for-rent is the highest level of 4.40, followed by resident behavior at 4.37, customer base building is 4.36, management is 4.34, and value selection is 4.32, respectively.
2. Summary of objective findings 2 to study the influence of corporate management, customer base building, value, selection, and resident behavior on the effectiveness of modern corporate management in rental apartments.
 - 2.1 It can be described as a relationship influence path that organizational management is directly related to building a customer base, as much as 0.90. This is followed by a direct result in the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments, equal to 0.21, but it does not directly affect value selection and resident behavior, equal to 0.04 and 0.01, respectively. And it indirectly affects the value, selection, resident behavior, and effectiveness of modern corporate management in apartment-for-rent housing, equal to 0.82, 0.83, and 0.79, respectively.
 - 2.2 It can be described as a path of influence, a relationship that building a customer base results in a direct result in value selection, as much as 0.91. This is followed by a direct effect on the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments, equal to 0.21, but not directly affecting resident behavior, equal to 0.01, and indirectly affecting the behavior of residents, and the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments is between 0.87 and 0.60, respectively.
 - 2.3 It can be described as a path of influence that value selection has the most direct effect on resident behavior, equal to 0.96, followed by a direct effect on the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartment housing, equal to 0.34, and indirectly affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartment housing, equal to 0.32.
 - 2.4 It can be described as a correlational influence pathway that resident behavior directly affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management in rental apartment housing, equal to 0.34.

3. To study the model of increasing the effectiveness of modern enterprise management, apartment-for-rent housing. A summary of the findings from quantitative and qualitative research has the following characteristics:

3.1 Quantitative research, organizational management, customer base building, value, selection, and occupancy behavior impact the effectiveness of modern corporate management strategies for rental apartments. The finding that corporate management affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments is statistically significant at the level of 0.05 can be interpreted as, as more corporate management results in an increase in the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments. And building a customer base affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management. Apartments rented statistically significantly at the level of 0.05 can be interpreted as increasing customer base is established. As a result, there is an increase in the effectiveness of modern enterprise management of rental apartments. Value selection affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments statistically at a level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as an increasing value selection, resulting in an increase in the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments. And resident behavior affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment housing statistically significant at a level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as increasing resident behavior. As a result, the effectiveness of modern enterprise management of rental apartments has also increased.

3.2 Quality research 1) Action plans, human resources and technology are important elements in the management of apartment-rental housing organizations, because the administration must carry out regulations or requirements under the relevant Acts. Management performs service tasks for customers or target audiences 2) Advertising, good service, and special promotions are elements of building a customer base and have consequences for managing the organization 3) Based on interviews with entrepreneurs' perspectives, the findings are that modernity, safety and comfort are directly attributed to customers or target audiences. Actions must be taken to understand what is most important in meeting the needs of the target customers of that organization 4) Personal attributes, rental period and impressions The importance must begin with building good relationships with customers in order to impress and other secondary factors and 5) The effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments has a component of factors in customer response, sustainable performance, and business partnerships, with all three factors interrelated, operations having to prioritize which factors will be implemented before or after.

Based on the above findings, the summary of the increase in the effectiveness of modern corporate management of apartment-for-rent housing, defined patterns, can be characterized as follows:

Figure 2: Increasing efficiency of modern corporate management, apartment-for-rent housing

In Figure 2, corporate management, with action plans, human resources and technology, is the key to success. Management is a relevant requirement, regulation, regulation or act, and management is a customer service job that relies on the science and art of entrepreneurs and employees to link factors. Such as the behavior factors of the residents. With modernity, safety, comfort and customer base building, good service, promotion and advertising, it is a tool to drive the organization according to its objectives. Meeting customer needs, sustainable impact and business partnerships are the ultimate goals.

Discussion

1. Discuss the test results of structural model equations.

1.1 Corporate Management this explains that building a child base is the management of service-related tasks for organizational goals. This is followed by a direct impact on the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment housing, and occupant behavior, respectively. It explains that the management of a fruitful organization should be administered in accordance with the requirements. Regulations or regulations for managing in accordance with the customer service segment, for affecting resident behavior, are described as having to operate with both administrative and management segments and indirectly affect the selection of value, resident behavior, and the effectiveness of modern management of rental apartment housing, respectively, which explains that management of work based on other factors helps promote and support.

1.2 Discuss the value of theoretical concepts.

Human Resources and Technology Action Plan It is significantly important to the management of the organization, recognized by the high level of technology, followed by human resources and action plans, respectively. This is consistent with qualitative findings and is consistent with Drucker's (2005) study that modern organizational management must carefully consider all the

dimensions that exist today to be able to carry out the organization's work towards the goals of achieving the most effective and effective achievements, including leading, human resources, planning, technology, organizing, and communication.

Advertising, good service and special promotions it is statistically significant for building a significant customer base. Recognized with special promotions, there is a high level of value. Followed by good service and advertising respectively. The results are consistent with qualitative findings. And it is in line with the educational concept of Abhisada Dinmung and Krishda Chierawatanasuk (2018), who said that building a customer base is maintaining market share in extremely competitive circumstances. Residential rental businesses need to be equipped with financial, personnel, physical, advertising, good service, and special promotions to motivate customers. This requires knowledge readiness, understanding of good relationship management between business and customer. With the aim of customer care, the goal is to maximize customer satisfaction or exceed the customer's commitment to service, create customer loyalty to the business, leading to the power of word-of-mouth communication for marketing purposes.

Modernity, safety and comfort statistically significant, statistically significant. This is evidenced by the high level of comfort, followed by security and modernization, respectively. The results are consistent with qualitative findings. This is in line with the educational concept of Boonsri Sutthirachai (2017) that says that comfort is the convenience of tenants getting in and out and having a sense of comfort or physicality in their stay or lifestyle, or having facilities and environments conducive to living. Based on the location of the apartment, the trust of the owner as the landlord understands the tenant will provide and provide the facilities.

Personal features, rental periods and impressions there is a statistically significant significance to resident behavior. As realized by the rental period, personal attributes have a high level of value, followed by impressions, respectively. The results are consistent with qualitative findings. And it is in line with the educational concepts of Veeraphat Buddhasarak and Chonlathit Darawong (2018) said tenant behavior affects the importance of housing marketing strategies and the length of time they rent.

Meeting customer needs, sustainable performance and business partnerships significantly, the effectiveness of modern corporate administration, residential units, and rental apartments. As evidenced by meeting customer needs, sustainability performance has a high level of value, followed by business partnerships, respectively. The results are consistent with qualitative findings. This is in line with the study concepts of Avey, Avolio, Crossley & Luthans (2009), which says that meeting customer needs is a strategy that results in perceived value and a level of comparative awareness between the quality of goods and services received and the price of a particular product. It also results in a unique sense of self-identity, which is a dimension of psychological belonging that comes from the basic principle of meeting the customer's needs.

Suggestion

1. Findings on the condition of variables

1.1 Findings and Recommendations 1: Organizational management affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment housing. It was found that technology has the greatest impact. It can be described as bringing technology. Social media is becoming an increasingly operational tool in management and management, increasing the effectiveness of the organization.

1.2 Findings and Recommendations 2: Building a customer base affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment housing. It was found that good service has the greatest impact. It explains that good service, hospitality, friendship and good relationships with customers are at the heart of the service, where such good service will instil the organization with customers towards building a base of children both new and old.

1.3 Findings and Recommendations 3: Value selection affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment housing. It was found that comfort has the greatest effect. It explains that considering choosing to rent a residential apartment, the client will choose from the convenience. Therefore, the management and management of entrepreneurs or employees should be important to facilitate comfort for customers.

1.4 Findings and Recommendations 4: Resident behavior affects the effectiveness of modern corporate management of rental apartments. It explains that personal behavior affects the rental and length of stay, so if it gives the customer an impression of the service, etc., it will inevitably affect the operation.

1.5 Findings and Recommendations 5 The effectiveness of modern enterprise management in apartment-for-rent housing has found that meeting customer needs with sustainable performance has the greatest impact. It can be explained that meeting customer needs with sustainable performance is an important foundation of management and management. Entrepreneurs and employees need to be aware, because without seeing the importance of such factors, the organization may not succeed at all.

2. Suggestions for future research

2.1 There should be studies on factors that encourage the client's decision to rent apartments in tourist destinations are believed to be the voices of each province.

2.2 There should be studies on management of the apartment management system should be studied effectively.

2.3 There should be studies on the effectiveness of the use of information technology in the management of residential rental apartments.

2.4 There should be studies on factors that contribute to the client's decision to rent an apartment

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